

cultural practices to favor high GM buildup, including close spacing (15 × 15 cm), continuous standing water of 2-5 cm, and frequent N application. Susceptible checks Jaya in Cuttack and TN1 in Sakoli were interspersed in the plots at the beginning, end, and after every 10 test entries to serve as indicators for GM buildup. Only plants completely free from infestation were rated resistant (R), while those showing any infestation rated susceptible (S).

TN1 had 100% GM-infested hills and 75-89% infested tillers (silvershoots). Jaya had 99-100% infested hills and 59-73% infested tillers.

Brown planthopper (BPH)-resistant varieties developed at Moncompu, Kerala

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The BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) has caused extensive damage to Asian rice crops. Although the pest was reported in Kerala during 1958 and 1962, the first severe outbreak occurred in 1973-74, damaging about 50,000 ha of rice. Grain yield loss was 10-70% and at times reached 100%.

Host plant resistance is the logical approach to BPH control.

Breeding programs for BPH-resistant varieties began in 1973 at RRS. BPH-

Damage ratings were consistent in both years at both centers. Entries S in Sakoli but R in Cuttack were ARC5158, ARC6221, RPW6-4 (S.S), Leaug 152, Shakti, Samalei, OB677, Orumundakan, CR294-548, CR3 17-166, CR319-644, CR315-621, CR318-548-7, CR410-3225, CR410-3225-2, CR308-408, CR309-268, ARC5984, Swimphul, CR394-6056, CR410-6018, and CR392-5085-2.

Entries R in both Sakoli and Cuttack were AC1224, MNP76, PTB10, Banglei, CR57-MR 1523, CR311-134, CR157-212, Aganni, Eswarakorra, Velluthacheera, NHTA 8, and T1477.

resistant donors such as PTB20, Kochuvithu, Karivennel, IR1539, PTB33, ARC6650, and IR1561, and modern varieties such as IR8, IR11, Triveni, and Jaya were used.

Promising selections were obtained from crosses IR8/PTB20, IR11/Kochuvithu, IR8/Karivennel, Trivenil IR1539, Jaya/PTB33, ARC6650/Jaya, and IR1561/PTB33. Eight varieties were released from them during 1978-90.

We studied the reaction of seedlings to the local BPH biotype using the bulk seedling test. Varieties were also screened in the field under heavy natural incidence. Resistance was scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. Results are presented in the table. □

Plant characters and BPH score of selections bred for BPH resistance in Kerala, India.

Variety	Parentage	Plant height (cm)	Crop duration (d)	Panicles (no./hill)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Grain type ^a	Protein content (%)	Reaction to BPH ^b		Release (year)
								Lab	Field	
MO 4 (Bhadra)	IR8m/PTB20	81	120 ^c 135 ^d	20.0	5.5	SB	10.2	2.8	2.5	1978
MO 5 (Asha)	IR11/Kochuvithu	85	120	7.5	6.0	LB	9.4	2.6	2.5	1980
MO 6 (Pavizham)	IR8/Karivennel	90	120	7.5	6.0	SB	7.5	2.0	2.3	1982
MO 7 (Karthika)	Triveni/IR1539	90	110	7.5	6.5	LB	10.6	2.0	2.0	1985
MO 8 (Aruna)	Jaya/PTB33	90	110	12.0	6.5	MB	9.6	2.2	1.7	1990
MO 9 (Makam)	ARC6650/Jaya	85	110	12.0	6.5	SB	9.4	1.7	2.5	1990
MO 10 (Remya)	Jaya/PTB33	110	120	10.0	6.5	LB	10.9	2.3	2.6	1990
MO 11 (Kanakam)	IR1561/PTB33	110	125	8.0	7.0	MB	9.5	1.6	2.0	1990
TN1 (susceptible check)		75	105	12.0	—	MB	—	9.0	9.0	—
PTB33 (resistant check)		135	130	6.0	—	MB	—	2.7	2.3	—

^a Cooking quality of all selections was good. SB = short bold, LB = long bold, MB = medium bold. All test varieties have red kernels.

^b By the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. ^c Dry season. ^d Wet season.

Orumundakan and its derivatives CR308-408 and CR309-268 were R in NCAP but S in Sakoli, Eswarakorra was R in Sakoli but S in NCAP, and Velluthacheera was S in NCAP but R at Sakoli. Sakoli GM was also different from that in Ranchi (III). CR57-MR 1523 was R in Sakoli and S in Ranchi; Kakatiya was the opposite.

Eswarakorra was R at both locations. PTB10 and its derivatives R296-120 and CR157-212 were R at all locations. Sakoli GM populations should be treated as a distinct biotype based on these results. □

Pest resistance—other pests

Upland rice cultivars resistant to parasitic weed *Striga hermonthica*

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Striga spp. are parasitic weeds of maize, sorghum, millet, and upland rice in Africa. No single method exists for controlling striga effectively. The pink-colored *S. hermonthica* (Del.) Benth. has become a serious problem in upland rice in western Kenya. We studied whether rice cultivars differed in relative resistance to *S. hermonthica*.

Forty upland rice lines from various sources were evaluated for reaction to striga during the 1990 short-rains cropping season (Sep-Dec). We conducted the experiment in a farmer's field that had a history of striga incident at Mbita Point under rainfed upland conditions (900 mm rain/yr). The soil is a calcaro-vertic Fluvisol with pH 8.1 and 0.9% organic C; each 100-g sample has CEC 37.5 meq, 0.1 meq K, and 36 meq P. Rice was planted in rows, 30 cm apart in 3- × 5-m plots, with four replications.

Striga plants were uprooted from plots at 95 d after rice emergence, dried, and weighed. Rice entries IR38547-B-B-7-2-2, IR47255-B-B-5-4, IR47697-4-3-1, and IR49255-B-B-5-2 were striga-free

Dry weight of striga plants uprooted from field plots planted to selected rice entries at 2 sites in South Nyanza District, western Kenya. ^a

Entry	Mbita Point, 1990 short rains		Ungoye, 1991 long rains	
	Dry wt (g/15m ² ± SD)	Rating ^b	Dry wt (g/15 m ² ± SD)	Rating ^b
IR38547-B-B-7-2-2	0.0 ± 0.0	HR	0.0 ± 0.0	HR
IR47255-B-B-5-4	0.0 ± 0.0	HR	6.0 ± 7.1	R
IR47697-4-3-1	0.0 ± 0.0	HR	0.0 ± 0.0	HR
IR49255-B-B-5-2	0.0 ± 0.0	HR	2.5 ± 3.8	R
B3913F-16-5-ST-42	4.5 ± 0.6	R		
Ble Chai	7.5 ± 0.6	R	6.5 ± 7.9	R
UPR103-80-1-2			6.0 ± 1.6	R
Nam Roo	1520.0 ± 45.8	HS	105.3 ± 156.8	S
ITA257	1251.0 ± 95.0	HS	73.0 ± 78.8	S
IR47686-B-B-2-2	1460.0 ± 90.0	HS	553.3 ± 811.4	HS
(susceptible check)				
IR47686-13-2-1	^c		489.0 ± 757.6	HS
CV	10.8		304.9	

^aData selected from 40 entries. ^bR = highly resistant, R = resistant, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible. ^cNot tested.

and rated as highly resistant (see table). Entries B3913F-16-5-ST-42 and Ble Chai had light infestation and were rated as resistant. The remaining striga-infested, stunted entries had drought-

like, leaf-wilting symptoms and were rated as susceptible to highly susceptible.

Ten entries were reevaluated during 1991 long-rains season (Mar-Jul) at

Ungoye (Eutric Cambisols, pH 6.1, CEC 48.2 meq/100 g soil, 0.2% N, 1.6% organic C, 98 meq P/100 g soil, 1,000 mm rainfall), about 40 km southwest of MPFS.

We planted entries in 3- x 5-m plots, replicated four times, in a randomized block design. Striga plants were removed 90 d after rice emergence from plots, dried, and weighed. Two of the four cultivars rated as highly resistant at Mbita Point were also highly resistant at Ungoye. Nam Roo and ITA257, rated as susceptible at Mbita Point, were moderately resistant to *S. hermonthica* at Ungoye, indicating a possible genetic variability of the populations. Check IR47686-B-B-2-2 was susceptible at both sites.

Our tests showed that some of these rice cultivars can possibly be used to breed for striga resistance in upland rice. □

Stress tolerance—drought

Performance of shallow water rice for drought tolerance

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We evaluated 22 shallow water rice entries for drought tolerance under field conditions. The experiment was laid out

Drought tolerance of best yielding entries, Tamil Nadu, India, 1990. ^a

Initial Evaluation Trial no.	Cross or variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Plant height (cm)
11371	Pankaj/T141	2.3	101
10743	Orumundakam/CRR1	2.2	114
–	Pankaj	2.1	99
–	Salivahana	1.8	105
11522	Mahsuri/IR2071-176-1-1	1.2	90
9866	Pankai/Swarnadhan	1.2	105
	LSD (P = 0.05)	0.4	7

^aNo yield was measured for IET10658 (Phalguna/PTB21/PTB33), IET10717 (Phalguna/Andrewsali), IET10722 (Nagarjuna/ARC5984), IET10738 (IR36/OR127-1), IET10754 (Phalguna/Andrewsali), IET10761 (Nagarjuna/ARC5084), IET10785 (Phalguna/Andrewsali), IET10797 (CR149-288/T142), IET11524 (IR20/IR25), IET11525 (IR20/IR15), IET11537 (CR151/CR1014), IET11537 (Nagarjuna/Magila), IET311374 (CR130-36/Jaganath), IET11395 (IET6858/ARC6172), IET11396 (IET6858/ARC6172), and Nagarjuna.

in a randomized block design with three replications. Seeds were sown 25 Jun 1990 and transplanted on 19 Jul 1990 in the main field in 7- x 2-m plots and at spacing of 15 x 10 cm.

The crop was irrigated every 10 d until 55 days after sowing (DAS) after which irrigation was stopped. Rains occurred at 120-125 DAS (110 mm) and 150-165 DAS (200 mm). We scored drought tolerance and drought recovery at 105 DAS and 125 DAS using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. All rice entries were grown to maturity.

Drought during late vegetative phase (55-110 DAS) and milk stage (125-140 DAS) severely affected the entries. Only six of the 22 entries yielded grain (see table). All six had tip drying to 1/4 of the length of most leaves. The nonyielding entries were chaffy and had unfilled grains because of the drought at the milk stage.

IET11371, IET10743, and Pankaj recorded yields of ≥ 2.1 t grain/ha, and 70-89% of the plants recovered. In contrast, Salivahana, IET11522, and IET9866 yielded 1.2-1.8t grain/ha, apparently because only 40-60% of plants recovered. □

Stress tolerance—excess water

Screening of rice germplasm against natural flooding in Cambodia

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We collected 1,600 samples of traditional rice germplasm in 1990-91 from 13 of

Cambodia's 21 provinces with the help of officials in the Ministry of Agriculture's Agronomy Department. Most of the cultivars were from rainfed lowland fields. Apparent duplicates were removed, leaving 373 new cultivars. These were direct seeded on 13 Aug 1991 at Prey Phdau Research Station, Kampong Speu. Twenty-two of the 373 did not germinate. Floodwater inundated the field 8 d after sowing. Seedlings